

A scanning electron micrograph (SEM) showing several large, spherical, pink-colored cells with a highly textured, bumpy surface. These cells are surrounded by smaller, green-colored cells with a more irregular, leaf-like or web-like structure. The background is black, making the cells stand out prominently.

Treating non-small cell lung cancer

What do patients PREFER?

prefer.

Treating lung cancer: Patient preferences

Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer sometimes called non-small cell lung carcinoma, or NSCLC for short) is the most common form of lung cancer and among the deadliest. It represents approximately 85% of all types of lung cancer worldwide and only 21.7% of patients diagnosed with this type of cancer are alive five years after being diagnosed. In order to help patients, different types of treatments are available for this condition. Traditional medical treatments for advanced stages of non-small cell lung cancer include chemotherapy and/or targeted radiotherapy. Now, there is a promising new type of treatment called immunotherapy.

All cancer treatment options come with their own set of benefits and risks. Benefits are related to extending length of life or improving symptoms. Benefits are positive aspects. Risks are related to side effects of the treatment or bad outcomes. Risks are negative aspects.

Little is known about which aspects or attributes of treatments patients with non-small cell lung cancer are most concerned about, or what risks they are willing to accept to obtain certain benefits.

We wanted to learn about lung cancer patients' preferences for new treatments, and what they considered to be the maximum acceptable risk, and the minimum acceptable benefit of a treatment.

Patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer have a choice in treatment options (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, target therapy, immunotherapy), between either a combined approach with immunotherapy followed by chemotherapy, or immunotherapy alone. Combined immunotherapy and chemotherapy has been shown to be more effective in fighting aggressive cancers than immunotherapy alone. However, this combination treatment can also cause more side effects, including some that are medically important like feeling very tired or sick to your stomach.

Since these cancer treatments are different in terms of both their benefits and risks, there is no single treatment option that is right for everyone.

What is immunotherapy?

Immunotherapy is a type of treatment that helps your immune system fighting cancer.

Sometimes, a combination of more than one treatment is used. Common combinations of therapies include:

- Immunotherapy first, followed by chemotherapy treatment later;
- Chemotherapy and immunotherapy at the same time; or
- Chemotherapy, immunotherapy and targeted radiotherapy.

As a result, the right treatment selection depends on a shared decision between the patient and multidisciplinary team and based on individual patient's preferences regarding the 'trade-off' between different benefits and risks. This is what we call a "preference-sensitive" situation.

Example of a preference-sensitive decision

A patient is faced with choosing, in consultation with an oncologist, between two treatments. The first treatment is very effective in prolonging life but causes severe tiredness so that the patient cannot take care of themselves. The second treatment effectiveness is uncertain, it might be effective as much as the first treatment or less, depending on specific characteristics of the patient, but has less impact on the patient's quality of life.

What were the patients' preferences?

We learned that there were **certain characteristics** of new medicines that were important to patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer. These characteristics included certain *positive* effects, certain *negative* effects, and *uncertainties* about how long each effect lasted ("duration" of effects).

Positive Treatment Characteristics

Patients identified the four most important positive treatment characteristics as being

1. Increase in life expectancy
2. Decrease in cancer growth
3. Decrease in the likelihood of cancer returning (remission), and
4. Does not affect their ability to carry out daily activities.

Negative Treatment Characteristics

Patients identified the 8 most important negative treatment characteristics as being:

1. Skin problems
2. Vomiting
3. Serious infections
4. Hair loss
5. Reactions associated with the drug being delivered via infusion
6. Being very tired
7. Likelihood of having their kidneys stop working, and
8. Likelihood of having problems thinking and/or with their memory ("cognitive" problems).

We also wanted to know more about the maximum acceptable risk and the minimum acceptable benefit that patients would be willing to accept for treatment alternatives. In a second phase of the research, a survey was conducted among non-small cell lung cancer patients to understand what trade-offs they were willing to make among 5 different treatment attributes. Results showed that patients preferred treatments:

- **With a higher 5-year survival (this was the most important aspect)**
- **A lower probability of long-lasting skin problems**
- **A lower probability of extreme tiredness, and**
- **Causing some or no hair loss over complete loss of hair.**

In terms of trade-offs, patients were willing to accept a substantially increased chance of developing side effects (long-lasting skin problems, or extreme tiredness, or complete air loss) in exchange for the slightest chance of surviving at least 5 years from the diagnosis of cancer

Why is this research important for patients?

Overall, patients with non-small cell lung cancer are willing to accept treatment-related risks if it increases their probability of living longer. This is perhaps not surprising considering the high mortality rate in lung cancer. In mathematical terms this means that:

- For every 1% increase in chance of 5-year survival, they were willing to accept an 8.5% increase in the probability of long-lasting skin problems;
- For every 1% increase in chance of 5-year survival, they were willing to accept a 6% increase in the probability of extreme tiredness;
- For a 1.6% increase in chance of 5-year survival, they were willing to switch from only taking a pill at home for treatment to having to stay in the hospital for 24 hours to get an infusion;
- For every 5% increase in chance of 5-year survival, they were willing to accept switching from no hair loss to complete hair loss.

This confirms results from previous studies in other types of cancer which also found that patients overwhelmingly rated living longer as the most important treatment attribute.

How the results will be used

Lung cancer treatment decisions are “preference-sensitive” in that the “best” treatment depends on an individual's values for particular health outcomes. Although the results must be interpreted with caution, pharmaceutical companies can use this information when making decisions about what kinds of treatments to develop. For example, the fact that patients gave more weight to an increase in life expectancy over other positive treatment characteristics might encourage companies to develop drugs for advanced (metastatic) cancer that extend life expectancy but cause more side effects. Regulatory authorities who approve new drugs for use in treating lung cancer may use this information and allow drugs with more risks for side effects to be used in clinical care if the treatment also provides clear benefits that patients want. Lastly,

Health Technology Assessment bodies (the authorities that decide whether a new drug will be reimbursed by health insurers) can use this information to decide whether new treatments should be covered by insurance because they meet patient needs.

How we did the research (methodology)

This research consisted of two parts: a qualitative study and a quantitative study. The qualitative study answered the question of what attributes of non-small cell lung cancer treatments matter most to these patients. The quantitative study measured what risks and benefits are acceptable to patients. More information on these studies can be found below.

Qualitative Study

We wanted to know what 'attributes' matter most to non-small cell lung cancer patients when selecting a treatment for lung cancer. The study included both men and women, aged 18 or older, living in either Belgium or Italy. All participants had a confirmed diagnosis of non-small cell lung cancer. In the end, participants were between 47-78 years old, with an average of 58 at the time they received their diagnosis. The majority were men (62%), and 38% were women.

In total, 6 focus groups were conducted (3 in Italy and 3 in Belgium). The information collected from these focus groups was used to identify common concerns about treatment. Participants were then asked to rank these concerns in order of importance.

Quantitative Study

We wanted to know what patients consider to be the maximum acceptable risk (in this case, specific negative effects) and the minimum acceptable benefit (in this case, the chance of 5-year survival) that they would accept for treatment alternatives.

We used an online survey to ask 307 patients with NSCLC from Italy and Belgium. Participants were asked to complete a series of questions regarding their willingness to trade off different treatment attributes, all of which had been identified via the qualitative study. Five different treatment attributes, each with 3 levels, were included in the survey:

- How the treatment is given to you
- Chance of surviving 5 years after starting this cancer treatment
- Chance of long lasting skin problems
- Chance of being extremely tired
- Severity of hair loss

Want to know more about the study?

More information about this research can be found on the PREFER website (www.imi-prefer.eu). The lead researchers who worked on this study are listed below. They can be reached if you have further questions about this study:

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About this study

Study Identification: The study is registered (#190183-001) on the Health Preference Study and Technology Registry which can be accessed at:
<https://hpstr.org/record/190183/001/029/entry>

Data Privacy and Ethics Approval: This study was conducted in accordance with General Data Privacy Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) and with ethics board approval (European Institute of Oncology IRCCS, Milan, Italy and at KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium).

Study title: PREFER project case study: Patient preferences for Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer treatment options

Study protocols are available at:

Monzani, D., Petrocchi, S., Oliveri, S., Veldwijk, J., Janssens, R., Bailo, L., ... & Huys, I. (2021). Patient Preferences for Lung Cancer Treatments: A Study Protocol for a Preference Survey Using Discrete Choice Experiment and Swing Weighting. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 8.

Durosini, I., Janssens, R., Arnou, R., Veldwijk, J., Smith, M. Y., Monzani, D., ... & Huys, I. (2021). Patient Preferences for Lung Cancer Treatment: A Qualitative Study Protocol Among Advanced Lung Cancer Patients. *Frontiers in public health*, 9, 27.

KU LEUVEN

ALEXION

Erasmus
University
Rotterdam

Erasmus

prefer.

PATIENT PREFERENCES

Want to know more? Go the PREFER project's website: www.imi-prefer.eu

The Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER) project has received funding from the [Innovative Medicines Initiative 2](#) Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 115966. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's [Horizon 2020](#) research and innovation programme and the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations ([EFPIA](#)). This report and its contents reflect the PREFER project's view and not the view of IMI, the European Union or EFPIA

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Cover image photo by National Cancer Institute on Unsplash. An important part of the immune system is its ability to keep itself from attacking normal cells in the body. To do this, it uses “checkpoint” proteins on immune cells, which act like switches that need to be turned on (or off) to start an immune response. Cancer cells sometimes use these checkpoints to avoid being attacked by the immune system.

Drugs that target these checkpoints (called checkpoint inhibitors) can be used to treat some people with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). These drugs can be used in different situations to treat NSCLC. In some cases, before one of these drugs can be used, lab tests might need to be done on the cancer cells to show they have at least a certain amount of the PD-L1 protein (checkpoint inhibitors) which would mean these drugs are more likely to work.

Source: <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/lung-cancer/treating-non-small-cell/immunotherapy.html>

Image (scales) from Pixabay by ArtsyBeeKids

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